

Standardisation guidelines and support materials

Project Title	CEI-Sphere, part of EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu
Project Acronym	CEI-Sphere
Project Number	101189683
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA
Topics	HORIZON-CL4-2024-DATA-01-05
Starting date of Project	1 October 2024
Duration of the project	30 months
Website	https://www.eucloudedgeiot.eu/

D4.2 – Standardisation guidelines and support materials

Work Package	WP4 Strategic architectures and standards
Task	4.2 Specification of standardisation roadmaps on prioritised topics Engagement for synergetic building blocks
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Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/05/2026
Submission Date	29/05/2026

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

CEI-Sphere - part of the broader EUCloudEdgeIoT community, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under Grant Agreement no. 101189683.

Versioning history

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	01/04/2026	Antonio KUNG (TRIA)	Creation of Deliverable Template and initial outline
0.2	15/05/2026	Antonio Kung (TRIA)	First draft
0.3	23/05/2025	Cécile Rabrait, Estibaliz Arzoz, Leo Cornec (TRIA)	Second draft
0.4	26/05/2026	Damir Filipovic (BLU)	Review
1.0	29/05/2026	Damir Filipovic (BLU)	Final editing for submission.

Abbreviations and Glossary

Abbreviation	Description
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
MIM	Minimum Interoperability Mechanism
TK	Toolkit element
VCIO	Value – Criteria – Indicators - Observables

Keywords

Ecosystem; Hourglass; Data space; CEI asset; Assurance; Trust

Terms

Terms	Definition
Asset	<p>ISO definition: Item, thing or entity that has potential or actual value to an organization (ISO 55000:2024 Asset management — Vocabulary, overview and principles).</p> <p>Comment 1: assets can be physical or non-physical..</p> <p>Comment 2: a grouping of assets or asset system can also be considered as an asset.</p>
Assurance	<p>ISO definition: grounds for justified confidence that a claim has been or will be achieved (ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-1:2025 Systems and software assurance — Part 1: Vocabulary and concepts)</p> <p>Comment 1: By definition, assurance is about a claim.</p> <p>Comment 2: The claim can be a conjunction of more than one claim.</p>
Dataspace or Data space	<p>ISO definition: Governance framework and supporting services to build trustworthiness and enable data sharing through an agreed set of policies, semantic models, protocols and processes (ISO/IEC DIS 20151 Dataspace concepts and characteristics)</p> <p>Comment: there is one dataspace per governance framework</p>
Ecosystem	<p>ISO definition: Infrastructure and services based on a network of organizations (3.13) and stakeholders. (ISO/IEC TS 27570:2021 Privacy guidelines for smart cities).</p> <p>Comment: in CEI-sphere, the structure of an ecosystem can be based on the hourglass model</p>
IT asset	<p>ISO definition: Item, thing, or entity that can be used to acquire, process, store and distribute digital information and has potential or actual value to an organization.</p> <p>Comment 1: IT assets include software, media (physical and digital), IT equipment (physical and virtual), licenses (including proof of license), contracts, and ITAM system management assets (including ITAM systems and tools, and the metadata needed to manage all IT assets).</p>

Terms	Definition
	<p>Comment 2: Services to meet IT asset management requirements, typically externally supplied, can also be considered IT assets, such as 'software-as-a-service', hardware maintenance, software support, and training.</p>
IT asset management (ITAM)	<p>ISO definition: coordinated activity of an organization to realize value from IT assets. (ISO/IEC 19770-1:2017 IT asset management — Part 1: IT asset management systems — Requirements)</p>
Trust (noun)	<p>ISO definition: Reliance on or belief in someone or something considering potential impacts within a defined context of use (ISO/IEC CD 31303 Trustworthiness — Overview and concepts)</p> <p>Comment 1: Impacts can be positive or negative.</p> <p>Comment 2: Trust implies accepting some risk.</p> <p>Comment 3: Trust can be supported by evidence. The acceptance of risk in a decision to trust is often underpinned by assurance mechanisms that provide justified confidence in the entity's trustworthiness</p> <p>Comment 4: Definition of trust is still under debate in ISO.</p>
Trustworthiness	<p>ISO definition: Ability to meet stakeholders' expectations in a verifiable way (ISO/IEC 5723:2022 Trustworthiness — Vocabulary)</p> <p>Comment 1: Depending on the context or sector, and also on the specific product or service, data, technology and process used, different characteristics apply and need verification to ensure stakeholders' expectations are met.</p> <p>Comment 2: Characteristics of trustworthiness include, for instance, accountability, accuracy, authenticity, availability, controllability, integrity, privacy, quality, reliability, resilience, robustness, safety, security, transparency and usability.</p> <p>Comment 3: Trustworthiness is an attribute that can be applied to services, products, technology, data and information as well as to organizations.</p> <p>Comment 4: Verifiability includes measurability and demonstrability by means of objective evidence.</p>

Acknowledgements

This document uses material from CEI-Sphere Deliverable [D4.1 \(CEI tech backbone toolkit for an open edge ecosystem. Checks & balances through a holistic assurance framework\)](#).

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides standardisation guidelines and support materials in the context of CEI-Sphere goal to support large scale pilots focusing on the Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) continuum.

It provides an introduction on the context of ecosystem, leveraging the hourglass model that was proposed by CEI-Sphere, and pointing out the growing number of regulations that involve the creation of harmonised standards.

It takes a data space perspective on ICT ecosystems and provides supporting material on related technology domains: data spaces, architecture, interoperability, trustworthiness, security and privacy, data, and artificial intelligence. Gaps and roadmaps are provided for each of these domains, showing that architecture in an ecosystem perspective (i.e. multiple organisation) and contextualisation (i.e. using generic horizontal standards and contextualising them to vertical domains) are key points to address in the standardisation roadmap

It then takes a CEI asset perspective and provides supporting material on related aspects: architecture patterns, minimum interoperability mechanisms, information model profiles, and CEI asset managements. Gaps and roadmaps are provided for each topic, showing again the need to take an ecosystem perspective and to address contextualisation issues.

It concludes by reminding of the work to be done in CEI-Sphere Task Force Open source, architecture, standards.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable provides a standard landscape document that is based on two perspectives:

- A data space perspective on ICT ecosystems.
- A cloud-edge-IoT (CEI) asset perspective based on an hourglass model focusing on architecture patterns, minimum interoperability mechanisms and information model profiles.

These two perspectives can be used by large scale pilots (LSPs) to frame their implementations:

- (1) in terms of standards to align with, and
- (2) in terms of standards to contribute to.

This work will then enable in the future, when pilots have progressed to switch to a domain perspective of a standard landscape. We plan to follow the proposed CEI spheres:

- Energy and infrastructure resilience.
- Mobility logistics and software defined vehicle (SDV).
- Industrial optimization and productivity.

1.2 About CEI-Sphere

CEI-Sphere is a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that aims to support the development of an open, interoperable, and competitive European ecosystem. This ecosystem encompasses the Cloud-Edge-IoT LSPs, particularly those funded under the CL4-2024-DATA-01-03 call, and their stakeholders. CEI-Sphere will play a constructive role in supporting the European Commission and the LSP community to achieve better outcomes, which include:

- Gaining a detailed understanding of the use cases, their maturity, their value chains, and their markets.
- Identifying horizontal challenges and synergies to help fast-track results.
- Supporting the development of open ecosystems through interoperability.
- Securing the interoperability, robustness, and scalability of CEI solutions through standards that can be promoted internationally.
- Connecting to technological, regulatory, and environmental drivers for CEI deployment, such as the mass adoption of generative AI (GenAI).

1.3 Structure of the Document

The content is structured into five sections:

- An introduction to CEI-Sphere,
- An introduction on the context of ecosystems, and regulation,
- A standard landscape from a data space perspective,
- A standard landscape from a CEI asset perspective,
- Conclusions and next steps.

Note: Text in boxes are excerpts from CEI-Sphere Deliverable [D4.1 – CEI tech backbone toolkit for an open edge ecosystem. Checks & balances through a holistic assurance framework.](#)

2. Context

2.1 Ecosystems - Using the Hourglass Model

CEI-Sphere has proposed the [hourglass model](#) ([slides](#), [video](#)) which has proved to be very effective for pilots to describe the ecosystem they are aiming at. The hourglass model was published in July 2025 by CEI-Sphere. Since then, many hourglass models have been provided by a wealth of projects:

- During the [AIOTI Days 2025](#) in September 2025, an introduction was provided on the [Hourglass model](#). A [video](#) discussion on smart cities was also presented, followed by:
 - An [hourglass](#) presentation from the [O-CEI](#) project.
 - An [hourglass](#) presentation from the [LICORICE](#) project.
 - An [Hourglass](#) presentation from the [TwinEU](#) project.
 - An [Hourglass](#) presentation from the [HEDGE-IoT](#) project.
 - An [Hourglass](#) presentation from the [STICS](#) project.
 - An [Hourglass](#) presentation from the [Eclipse dataspace working group](#).
- The [Open Source Community Day 2025](#) in March 2026 included:
 - An [hourglass](#) presentation from the [O-CEI](#) project.
 - An [hourglass](#) presentation from the [CONNECT](#) project.
 - An [hourglass](#) presentation from the [HEDGE-IoT](#) project.
 - An [hourglass](#) presentation from the [LICORICE](#) project.
- One standard under development, [PWI TR JTC1-SC41-33](#) (Digital Twin – Guidance on digital twin reference architecture) describes several hourglass models:
 - Digital twins for smart manufacturing.
 - Digital twins for smart cities.
 - Digital twins for citiverse.
 - Digital twins for smart grid

Reminder of the hourglass model

Figure 1 shows an hourglass model template that is used to analyse an ecosystem:

- **The left side** is used to position stakeholders along logical layers, such as application developers, dataspace stakeholders, platform and tool providers, infrastructure service providers or infrastructure providers.
- **The right side** is used to position
 - capabilities, such as user interfaces, data analytics, platforms and tools, cloud – edge - digital twin or AI services,
 - standards, and
 - open-source building blocks.
- **The narrow layer** focuses on key platform tool providers and capabilities that can have a business impact on the ecosystem.

Figure 1 – Hourglass model template

Several ecosystems can be created. Figure 2 shows four interdependent ecosystems, a data space ecosystem, a CEI ecosystem, a data space interoperability ecosystem and an IoT ecosystem.

Figure 2 – Multiple ecosystems in the context of CEI.

2.2 Regulations

The importance of ICT has led Europe to develop a wealth of regulation, many including standardisation requests which call for the development of harmonized standards. As stated by the [European Commission](#),

“A harmonised standard is a European standard developed by a recognised European Standards Organisation: CEN, CENELEC, or ETSI. It is created following a request from the European Commission to one of these organisations. Manufacturers, other economic operators, or conformity assessment bodies can use harmonised standards to demonstrate that products, services, or processes comply with relevant EU legislation.”

Table 1 lists European standardisation committees as well as the regulations for which harmonized standards are being developed.

Table 1. European standardisation committees and Harmonised standards

Committee	Regulation involving harmonized standards
CEN-CENELEC JTC 13	RED , CRA
ETSI TC Cyber	CRA
CEN-CENELEC JTC21	AI Act
CEN-CENELEC JTC24	ESPR
CEN-CENELEC JTC25	Data Act , Data Governance Act
ETSI TC Data	Data Act , Data Governance Act

Other regulations that have to be taken into account on cybersecurity and privacy include [GDPR](#), [NIS2](#), [DORA](#)¹, or [EUCC](#).

Figure 3 shows an hourglass model focusing on regulation. Note that the colour coding in the figure shows the correspondence between regulations and standardisation committees in charge of developing the harmonised standards addressing the regulation.

Figure 3 – Reusable conformity mechanisms

¹ When financial stakeholders are involved in applications where payment is involved.

3. Data Space-driven Standards

3.1 Guidelines

Figure 4 provides an example how standards can be identified according to their relations to data space standards. Each box in the figure is a standard and note that each box has a red or green tag indicating that the standard is under development or is published. The categories of standards are the following:

- Data space,
- Architecture,
- Interoperability,
- Trustworthiness,
- Security and privacy,
- Data, and
- Artificial intelligence.

The figure also shows that standards can belong to several categories. For instance, *SC41 301852 IoT and digital twins in data spaces* is both an architecture standard and a data space standard. These standards and others will be presented in the section on supporting materials.

Figure 4 – Example of standards dependencies

3.2 Supporting materials

3.2.1 Involved Committees

Table 2 lists examples of committees of interest to CEI-Sphere.

Table 2. Committees

Committee	Description
ISO/IEC JTC 1	Established in 1987 on information technology, has published over 3,600 standards and is currently developing more than 500 standards
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Established in 1989 on cybersecurity and privacy has published 252 standards and is developing about 72 standards
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32	Established in 2009 on cloud computing and distributed computing has published 33 standards, and is developing 13 standards
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Established in 2017 on IoT and digital twins has published 52 standards and is developing 24 standards
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	Established in 2017 on artificial intelligence has published 39 standards and is developing 45 standards
CEN-CENELEC JTC 13	Established in 2017 on cybersecurity and privacy
ETSI TC Cyber	Established on 2014 on cybersecurity
CEN-CENELEC JTC21	Established in 2021 on artificial intelligence
CEN-CENELEC JTC24	Established on 2023 on digital product passport
CEN-CENELEC JTC25	Established in 2024 on data exchange
ETSI TC Data	Established in 2025 on data solutions in line with the European data governance act

3.2.2 Dataspaces

Activities

Table 3 provides a selected list of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 and from CEN-CENELEC JTC25 focusing on data spaces.

Table 3. Data space standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC DIS 20151-1 Dataspaces. Part 1: Concepts and characteristics (in Figure 4)	Draft international standard	This document provides the foundational concepts and essential characteristics of dataspaces. This document is applicable to all organizations.
ISO/IEC NP 20151-2 Dataspaces. Part 2: Trust frameworks (in Figure 4)	Project under ballot approval	This document describes dataspace trust framework concepts and guidance for the development and comparison of dataspace trust frameworks, including their essential and optional elements and related aspects. This document is applicable to all organizations.

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC TR 25850 Use case for data spaces (in Figure 4)	Technical report under development	This document describes use cases for dataspace covering trusted data sharing scenarios, interoperability and business value at various levels and ecosystems based on ISO/IEC 20151 and ISO/IEC 19941.
ISO/IEC DIS 26451 Eclipse decentralized claims protocol (in Figure 4)	Draft international standard	Dataspace require the ability to communicate participant identities and credentials to secure data access. This specification defines a set of protocols for asserting participant identities, issuing verifiable credentials, and presenting verifiable credentials using a decentralized architecture for verification and trust.
ISO/IEC DIS 26450 Eclipse Dataspace Protocol (DSP) (in Figure 4)	Draft international standard	The Dataspace Protocol is a specification designed to facilitate interoperable data sharing between entities governed by usage control and based on Web technologies. This specification defines the schemas and protocols required for entities to publish data, negotiate Agreements, and access data as part of a federation of technical systems termed a Dataspace
CEN/CLC/TS 18331:2026 (WI=JT025010) Maturity assessment of Common European Data Spaces	Approved	This document provides a multi-dimensional assessment framework of data spaces maturity, considering the different needs of data spaces, their participants, domain, or scope. Specifically, it defines a maturity model concept, structure, methodology and measurable criteria, with related requirements and guidance for the assessment of data space maturity. This document applies to all types of organizations, regardless of their type or size.
prEN 18235-2 Trusted data transactions - Part 2: Trustworthiness requirements	Under approval	This document provides trustworthiness requirements and guidance for data space participants in support of trusted data transactions. Specifically, it defines a set of foundational principles for trusted data transactions, and establishes general requirements and guidance that apply to all phases of a trusted data transaction, and specific requirements for each phase of a trusted data transaction. This document applies to all types of organizations participating in data spaces, regardless of their type or size
prEN 18235-3 Trusted data transactions - Part 3: Interoperability requirements	Under approval	This document provides trustworthiness requirements and guidance for data space participants in support of trusted data transactions. Specifically, it defines a set of foundational principles for trusted data transactions, and establishes general requirements and guidance that apply to all phases of a trusted data transaction, and specific requirements for each phase of a trusted data transaction. This document applies to all types of organizations participating in data spaces, regardless of their type or size.
prEN 18352 Quality framework for internal	Under enquiry	This document defines a framework for assessing the quality of data governance and data management

Standard	Status	Description
data governance for participants in data spaces		<p>practices for participants in data spaces. It specifies the core principles, processes, and assessment elements that enable organizations to manage, monitor, and improve their data governance and data management practices. The framework comprises two components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process Reference Model: Defines key processes for data governance and data product management of data space participants, including its fundamental principles, structure, detailed process definitions, links to broader data governance, and required implementation measures. • Process Assessment Framework: Outlines a model to evaluate process capability by establishing six distinct quality levels expressed in terms of capability levels, describing the corresponding profiles and guiding the systematic assessment. <p>This standard is aimed at supporting data governance and data management professionals, IT managers, quality assurance officers, and regulatory bodies. This standard is applicable to organizations of all types and sizes.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Alignment of data space architectures
 - **Gap:** there is a need to align more precisely reference documents on data space blueprints in order to avoid siloes and get assurance of compatibility and interoperability between data spaces
 - **Roadmap:** alignment could be achieved by contributing work on data space reference architecture associated with architecture patterns.
- Contextualisation of data spaces
 - **Gap:** there is a need to support contextualisation of data spaces to support domain specific needs (technology domains and application domains).
 - **Roadmap:** contextualisation could be achieved by defining profiles, covering architecture, interoperability and trustworthiness aspects.

3.2.3 Architecture

Activities

Table 4 provides a selected lists of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1.

Table 4. Architecture standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC/IEEE DIS 42024 Architecture fundamentals	Draft international standards	<p>This document specifies the foundational vocabulary, concepts and principles associated with an architecture and used within the architecting practice for various entities, including software, systems, enterprises, missions, systems of systems, families of systems, infrastructures, products (goods or services), product lines, service lines, technologies and business domains. The vocabulary, concepts and principles apply to:</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organizations that develop architectures; • organizations seeking sustained success through the implementation of architecture practices; • organizations and interested parties seeking to improve communication through a common understanding of the vocabulary, concepts and principles used in architecture description; • organizations performing conformity assessments against the requirements of architecture-related standards and specifications; • providers of architecture descriptions, guidelines, training, education, evaluation or recommendations in architecture practices; • developers of architecture-related standards, architecture description languages, architecture modelling languages, reference architectures, reference models related to architecture, architecture frameworks and architecture-related tools/technologies. <p>The application areas of this document include, but are not limited to, the following: artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, big data, smart cities, smart manufacturing, cybersecurity, digital twin, telecommunications, aerospace, defence, banking, finance, insurance, energy, automotive, hospitality, healthcare, supply chain, transportation, manufacturing, agriculture, production, and infrastructure.</p> <p>This document addresses generic architecture-related terms and definitions and does not address domain-specific terms and definitions. This document does not address concepts and principles related to architecture competencies. The proposed deliverable is another document in the existing group of architecture related standards (e.g. ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010, ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020, ISO/IEC/IEEE 42030).</p>
ISO/IEC/IEEE DIS 42042 Reference architectures (in Figure 4)	Draft international standard	<p>This standard describes the requirements to be satisfied by domain-specific reference architectures that address entities of interest such as software, systems, enterprises, missions, systems of systems, families of systems, products (goods or services), product lines, service lines, technologies and business domains. The proposed standard will be universally applicable to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organizations seeking sustained success through the implementation of architecture practices, • organizations and interested parties seeking to improve communication through a common understanding of the vocabulary and concepts used in reference architectures, • organizations performing conformity assessments against the requirements of reference- architecture-related standards and specifications,

Standard	Status	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organizations that serve as certification authorities that will benefit from the use of reference architectures, • organizations that need to mandate use of reference architectures, • providers of reference architectures, guidelines, training, education, evaluation or recommendations in architecture practice, • developers of reference-architecture standards, reference models, and related tools/technologies, • users of reference architectures. <p>The application areas of this standard include, but are not limited to, the following: artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, big data, smart cities, smart manufacturing, cybersecurity, digital twin, telecommunications, aerospace, defense, banking, finance, insurance, energy, automotive, logistics, hospitality, healthcare, supply chain, transportation, manufacturing, agriculture, production, and infrastructure.</p> <p>The proposed deliverable is part of the ISO 42000 architecture standards (e.g., 42010, 42020, 42030).</p>
ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2022 Architecture description	Published in November 2022	<p>This document specifies requirements for the structure and expression of an architecture description (AD) for various entities, including software, systems, enterprises, systems of systems, families of systems, products (goods or services), product lines, service lines, technologies and business domains.</p> <p>This document distinguishes the architecture of an entity of interest from an AD expressing that architecture. Architectures are not the subject of this document.</p> <p>This document specifies requirements for use of the architectural concepts and their relationships as captured in an AD. It does not specify requirements for any entity of interest or its environment.</p> <p>This document specifies requirements for an architecture description framework (ADF), an architecture description language (ADL), architecture viewpoints and model kinds in order to usefully support the development and use of an AD.</p> <p>This document specifies conformance to the requirements for an AD, ADF, ADL, architecture viewpoint and model kind.</p> <p>This document does not specify the processes, architecting methods, models, notations, techniques or tools by which an AD is created, utilized or managed.</p> <p>This document does not specify any format or media for recording an AD.</p>

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020:2019 Architecture processes	Published in July 2019	<p>This document establishes a set of process descriptions for the governance and management of a collection of architectures and the architecting of entities. This document also establishes an enablement process description that provides support to these other architecture processes.</p> <p>The processes defined in this document are applicable for a single project, as well as for an organization performing multiple projects. These processes are applicable throughout the life of an architecture or a collection of architectures. These processes are applicable for managing and performing the activities within any stage in the life cycle of the architecture entities.</p> <p>Annex D describes the relationships between this document and other standards.</p>
ISO/IEC/IEEE 42030:2019 Architecture evaluation framework	Published in July 2019	<p>This document specifies the means to organize and record architecture evaluations for enterprise, systems and software fields of application.</p> <p>The aim of this document is to enable architecture evaluations that are used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) validate that architectures address the concerns of stakeholders; b) assess the quality of architectures with respect to their intended purpose; c) assess the value of architectures to their stakeholders; d) determine whether architecture entities address their intended purpose; e) provide knowledge and information about architecture entities; f) assess progress towards achieving architecture objectives; g) clarify understanding of problem space and of stakeholder needs and expectations; h) identify risks and opportunities associated with architectures; and i) support decision making where architectures are involved. <p>NOTE This document addresses the evaluation of an architecture and not an evaluation of the architecture description's suitability. Matters concerning the evaluation of the architecture description fall within the scope of the architecture conceptualization and architecture elaboration processes as defined in ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020. However, it is sometimes the case that the architecture description is evaluated concurrently with the evaluation of the architecture itself.</p> <p>The entity being evaluated can be of several kinds, as illustrated in the following examples: enterprise,</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		<p>organization, solution, system, subsystem, business, data (as a data element or data structure), application, information technology (as a collection), mission, product, service, software item, hardware item, etc. The kind of entity can also be a product line, family of systems, system of systems, etc. It also spans the variety of applications that utilize digital technology such as mobile, cloud, big data, robotics, Internet of Things (IoT), web, desktop, embedded systems, and so on.</p> <p>The generic Architecture Evaluation (AE) framework specified in this document can be used in support of the Architecture Evaluation process defined in ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020. Specific frameworks can be derived from this generic framework, which can provide a mapping to the system life cycle processes in ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 or to the software life cycle processes in ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207.</p>
ISO/IEC 30141:2024 Ed2 IoT reference architecture	Published in August 2024	<p>ISO/IEC 30141:2024 provides a standardized IoT Reference Architecture using a common vocabulary, reusable designs and industry best practices. It uses a top down approach, beginning with collecting the most important characteristics of IoT, and abstracting those into a foundational view, then providing five more views including a construction view with a set of architecture and design patterns for building IoT systems.</p> <p>This second edition cancels and replaces the first edition published in 2018. This edition constitutes a technical revision. This edition includes the following significant technical changes with respect to the previous edition:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> conformance with ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2022; improved usability; implementation pattern support.
ISO/IEC 30188 Digital twin reference architecture (in Figure 4)	Final draft international standard	<p>This document specifies a general reference architecture for a digital twin system in terms of defining system fundamentals through the use of architecture views.</p>
PWI TR JTC1-SC41-33 Digital Twin – Guidance on digital twin reference architecture	Under development	<p>This document provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> guidance on using the ISO/IEC 30188 – Digital Twin Reference Architecture, considerations on the use of digital twin technology in application domains, considerations on digital twin technology terminology.
PWI TR JTC1-SC41-22 Architecture considerations for IoT, edge and cloud (in Figure 4)	Under study	<p>Provide a technical report on the architecture in the IoT, edge and cloud with the goal to contribute to the reference architecture in the form of construction patterns.</p>
PWI JTC1-SC41-28 Distributed processing framework for massive	Under study	<p>In order to solve the massive data interoperability of Real-Time IoT systems:</p>

Standard	Status	Description
data interoperability of Real-Time IoT systems		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specifies the distributed processing structure and flow of massive real-time data of a large-scale network information service platform, Provides a unified name specification and definition description,
PNW JTC1-SC41-577 ED1 Data exchange platform for IoT services – Part 3: Requirements and functional definitions for remote control and monitoring	Under study	<p>This part of ISO/IEC 30161 specifies the following items for remote control and monitoring in the IoT data exchange platform (IoT DEP):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirements; System configuration; <p>Definitions of functional blocks.</p>
ISO/IEC 30152 ED1 IoT and digital twins – Guidance on the connection to data spaces (in Figure 4)	Under study	<p>This document provides guidance on the connection of IoT systems and digital twins in dataspace, including principles, architecture and lifecycle considerations. It is based upon</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> concepts and characteristics described in ISO/IEC 20151:2026 (Dataspace concepts and characteristics), architecture considerations described in ISO/IEC Ed2 30141:2024 Ed2 (IoT reference architecture) and ISO/IEC 30188:2026 (Digital twin reference architecture), and interoperability aspects described in ISO/IEC 21823 series (Interoperability for IoT systems).
ISO/IEC 30153 ED1 Digital twin – Process and guidance for digital twin model construction	Under study	<p>This document provides a process and guidance for digital twin model construction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> This document specifies: information preparation requirement; basic types of models of digital entity, the principles of development, the model verification and calibration. <p>This document is applicable for the digital twin development process for related research, applications, and services.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Interoperable architecture description
 - **Gap:** while architecture considerations are always present in most standards, a common architecture description approach is often missing, even though standards based on agreed practices, e.g. from the [INCOSE](#) community.
 - **Roadmap:** publishing and using common architecture patterns (1) to address complex systems and (2) to foster to reusability.
- Contextualisation
 - **Gap:** the support of application specific (e.g. health), or technology specific (e.g. safety) requires customisation of architecture while retaining common aspects.
 - **Roadmap:** defining architecture profiles will proper governance mechanisms to manage architecture common parts and specific parts.

3.2.4 Interoperability

Activities

Table 5 provides a selected lists of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC38, SC41, and ETSI TC-Data.

Table 5. Interoperability standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 21823-1 ED2 Interoperability for IoT systems - Part 1: Framework	Under development	<p>This document provides an overview of interoperability as it applies to IoT systems and a framework for interoperability for IoT systems. This document enables IoT systems to be built in such a way that the entities of the IoT system are able to exchange information and mutually use the information in an efficient way. This document enables peer-to-peer interoperability between separate IoT systems.</p> <p>This document ensures that all parties involved in building and using IoT systems have a common understanding of interoperability as it applies to IoT systems and the various entities within them.</p>
ISO/IEC 21823-5 ED1 Interoperability for IoT systems – Part 5: Behavioural and policy interoperability	Under development	<p>This part of ISO/IEC 21823 specifies interoperability from a behavioural and policy viewpoint. In this document, the following specifications for interoperability from policy and behavioural points of view are included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a principle on how to achieve behavioural and policy interoperability; • requirements on information related to behavioural and policy interoperability; and • a framework for the development of information exchange rules from a behavioural and policy viewpoint.
PWI JTC1-SC41-32 Digital Twin -- General requirements of information exchange	Under study	<p>This standard specifies the technical architecture of digital twin information exchange and identifies three types of interaction in digital twin information exchange, including measurement perception, feedback control, and interaction between digital entities. This standard defines the technical requirements for digital twin information interaction for three types of interactions.</p> <p>This standard defines the performance requirements for digital twin information exchange, including basic requirements, security requirements, and expansion requirements.</p> <p>This standard applies to the design, deployment, application and related product development of digital twins.</p>
PWI JTC1-SC41-38 Interoperability, compliance, and automation framework for autonomous Digital Twins	Under study	<p>This document provides a foundational framework addressing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability across digital twin ecosystems • Verification of automated twinning processes • Traceability, accuracy, and fidelity of twin integration • Distance- and device-agnostic synchronization

Standard	Status	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity assurance through digital passports • Compliance requirements for autonomous twin-enabled devices operating and self-regulating within regulated critical infrastructure sectors
ISO/IEC 19941-1 Cloud computing – Part 1: Interoperability and Portability	Draft international standard	<p>This document specifies cloud computing interoperability and portability types, the relationship and interactions between these two cross-cutting aspects of cloud computing and distributed platforms, as well as common terminology and concepts used to discuss interoperability and portability, particularly relating to cloud services.</p> <p>This document is related to other standards, including, ISO/IEC 22123 series, ISO/IEC 19086-1, ISO/IEC 19944-1, ISO/IEC 5140 and in particular, references the cross-cutting aspects and components identified in ISO/IEC 22123-1 and ISO/IEC 22123-3 respectively.</p> <p>The goal of this document is to ensure that all parties involved in cloud computing, particularly CSCs, CSPs and CSNs acting as cloud service developers, have a common understanding of interoperability and portability for their specific needs – including switching service provision from one CSP to another. This common understanding helps to achieve interoperability and portability in cloud computing by establishing common terminology and concepts.</p>
ETSI REN/DATA-00303760 work item (EN 303 760) Implementation framework for semantic assets Guidelines for Semantic Interoperability	2.0.0 draft for Harmonised standard	<p>The present document gives guidance and provisions for making data products within European data spaces interoperable at the semantic level in compliance with the SAREF framework.in the context of the EU trusted Data transaction standardization. It contains provisions about how to use SAREF, points to the relevant existing Technical Reports and Technical Specifications and specifies a methodology to follow for showing SAREF compliance according to the present SAREF EN. Further on, it describes how to contribute optionally to a new SAREF extension (if what Users need is not yet in the SAREF framework). IoT smart applications and products remain one important case covered by the present document, but the ontology domains shift to data products in data spaces, to support the semantic assets in the contest of the trusted data transactions.</p> <p>The present document addresses parties involved in the development and manufacturing of data products and data spaces, who might take different roles in their organization like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • executives and product owners, who decide whether to invest in a SAREF-compliant data products; • developers, who will implement a SAREF-compliant data products as non-ontology experts or even ontology experts. <p>Different roles imply different intentions and expectations when reading the present document according to their</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		tasks in the organization. The present document considers this by its implemented structure. Clause 4 provides guidance about how to go throughout the present document in order to judge, which clauses might be essential for the special role of the reader and which ones might be skipped.
ETSI DTR/DATA-00104244 work item (TR 104 244) Data Solutions (DATA); Implementation of Data Catalogues with NGSI-LD and DCAT-AP	0.6.0 Draft for harmonised standard	The present document aims at recommending an approach to encode metadata about datasets and data services in an NGSI-LD format that is aligned with Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) and its Application Profile (DCAT-AP) definitions.

Gaps and roadmaps

- Interoperability in ecosystems
 - **Gap:** interoperability is viewed in isolation, not in the context of the underlying ecosystem.
 - **Roadmap:** applying interoperability-by-design to ecosystems involving multiple organisations.
- Governance
 - **Gap:** lack of coordination between organisations involved in interoperability
 - **Roadmap:** define governance methods and practice them

3.2.5 Trustworthiness

Activities

Table 6 provides a selected lists of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 13, SC41, ISO/TC292.

Table 6. Trustworthiness standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 5723:2022 Trustworthiness vocabulary (in Figure 4)	Published in July 2022	This document provides a definition of trustworthiness of systems and their associated services along with a selected set of its characteristics.
ISO/IEC 31303 Trustworthiness overview (in Figure 4)	Under development	This document provides an overview of trustworthiness and related concepts and describes trustworthiness applicable to information technology (IT).
ISO/IEC 31310 Trustworthiness ontology (in Figure 4)	Under development	This document describes the ontology framework and the general ontological notion of trustworthiness for information technology.
ISO/IEC 30147 ED2 Integration of IoT trustworthiness activities in ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 system engineering processes	Under development	This document provides system life cycle processes to implement and maintain trustworthiness in an IoT system or service by applying and supplementing ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2023 . The system life cycle processes are applicable to IoT systems and services common to a wide range of application areas.

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 30149 IoT Trustworthiness principles (in Figure 4)	Published in 2024	This document provides elements of IoT trustworthiness based on the IoT reference architecture specified in ISO/IEC 30141
ISO 22373 Security and resilience — Authenticity, integrity and trust for products and documents — Framework for establishing trustworthy supply and value chains	Published in November 2025	<p>This document establishes a framework to support stakeholders in supply and value chains to ensure the chain of trustworthiness regarding the properties of their products and production processes.</p> <p>This document provides guidelines to identify information relevant to trustworthiness to be exchanged between supply and value chain stakeholders. It also provides an interoperable data structure that is required for supply and value chain stakeholders to negotiate and exchange information relevant to trustworthiness.</p> <p>The guidelines set out in this document are generic and are intended to be applicable to all organizations and products, regardless of type, size or nature.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Characterization of trustworthiness
 - **Gap:** characteristics of trustworthiness are numerous, from very technical characteristic (e.g. security) to very societal characteristic (e.g. ethics)
 - **Roadmap:** applying trustworthiness-by-design to ecosystems involving multiple organisations.
- Trustworthiness profiles and associated governance
 - **Gap:** agreeing on characteristics and associated requirements
 - **Roadmap:** define methods for trustworthiness characterization and governance.

3.2.6 Security and privacy

Activities

Table 7 provides a selected lists of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27.

Table 7. Security and privacy standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 27115-1 Cybersecurity of System of Systems — Part 1: Security Architecture Description (in Figure 4)	Under development	<p>This document provides a framework to specify the cybersecurity of complex systems, including systems of systems.</p> <p>The frameworks use basic architecture concepts to enable description of reference or solution security architectures.</p>
ISO/IEC 27115-2 Cybersecurity of System of Systems — Part 2: Security Architecture Evaluation (in Figure 4)	Under development	<p>This document provides a framework to evaluate the cybersecurity of complex systems, including systems of systems, based on ISO/IEC TS 27115-1.</p> <p>The frameworks use basic architecture concepts to support model-based, comprehensive and scalable security solutions and their evaluation.</p>

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 27115-3 Cybersecurity of System of Systems — Part 3: Security Profiles (in Figure 4)	Under development	<p>This document provides a framework to describe security profiles based on ISO/IEC TS 27115-1, ISO/IEC TS 27115-2.</p> <p>The frameworks use basic architecture concepts to enable the definition of architecture-based security profiles and composition of profiles.</p>
ISO/IEC TS 27116-1 Security and privacy - Part 1: Framework for multipurpose evaluation	Under ballot for development approval	<p>This document provides a framework for multipurpose evaluation of security and privacy, covering multiple organisations, multiple targets of evaluations, and multiple domains.</p> <p>This document is applicable to all organizations.</p>
ISO/IEC 27116-2 Security and privacy - Part 2: Examples of multipurpose evaluation Currently 26245	Under development	<p>This document provides an analysis of multipurpose security evaluation for IT products, including</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a best practice process example on how developers can maximize the value of a single security evaluation, and reuse its results for additional evaluations to support compliance with standards. • an analysis on how security assurance requirements can be reused.
ISO/IEC PWI 26601 Cybersecurity — Guidance for Addressing Cybersecurity of System of Systems	Under development	<p>This document provides guidance for addressing cybersecurity in systems of systems (SoS), including relevant concepts, generic security threats, and security concerns associated with the specialized characteristics of SoS.</p> <p>This document covers cybersecurity issues specific to the SoS context and thus complements generic cybersecurity standards and system engineering standards. In particular, this document provides security threats related to SoS characteristics such as heterogeneity, cascading, and lifecycle, and establish security concerns in SoS environments.</p> <p>This document is applicable to personnel and organizations engaged in the development, integration, operation, and maintenance of complex systems, such as large enterprises, small and medium-sized enterprises, assessment bodies, and regulatory authorities, to support the implementation and operation of relevant requirements in SoS security governance and risk management.</p>
ISO/IEC 27568 Security and privacy of digital twins (in Figure 4)	Under development	<p>This document provides guidance for organizations to address security and privacy risks in digital twin systems. The guidance in this document helps organizations identify security and privacy risks throughout the digital twin systems lifecycles and establishes mechanisms to evaluate the consequences of and treat such risks.</p> <p>This document is applicable to all types and sizes of organizations, including public and private companies,</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		government entities, and not-for-profit organizations, that develop or use digital twin systems.
ISO/IEC 5181 Security and privacy protection — Data provenance (in Figure 4)	Final draft international standard	This document provides guidelines, methodologies and techniques for deriving information securely from provenance metadata about data assets from multiple sources, intermediaries or users.
ISO/IEC 27564:2025 Privacy protection — Guidance on the use of models for privacy engineering (in Figure 4)	Published in September 2025	<p>This document provides guidance on how to use modelling in privacy engineering.</p> <p>It describes categories of models that can be used, the use of modelling to support engineering, and the relationships with other references, including International Standards on privacy engineering and on modelling.</p> <p>It provides high-level use cases describing how models are used.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Lack of security-by-design
 - **Gap:** while the strength of today standards is on organisational security, there is a lack of security engineering integration, of continuum of evaluation, and architecture support on security.
 - **Roadmap:** applying trustworthiness-by-design to ecosystems involving multiple organisations.
- Contextualisation and security and privacy profiles
 - **Gap:** agreeing on contextualised requirements
 - **Roadmap:** define methods for security and privacy profiles.

3.2.7 Data

Table 8 provides a selected lists of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC32, SC41.

Table 8. Data standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 30151 ED1 Digital Twin - Extraction and transactions of data products (in Figure 4)	Underway	<p>This document provides a framework on the extraction and transaction of data products in digital twins.</p> <p>This document is applicable to organizations (for example, commercial enterprises, government agencies, and not-for-profit organizations) or individuals providing data products from digital twins and exchanging data products in the dataspace.</p>
ISO/IEC 5207:2024 Data usage — Terminology and use cases (in Figure 4)	Published in April 2024	This document sets out terminology and use cases for data use, sharing and exchange. This document can be used in the development of other International Standards and in support of communications among diverse stakeholders and other interested parties. This document is applicable to all types of organizations (including commercial enterprises, government agencies, not-for-profit organizations).

Standard	Status	Description
		Users of this document can find ISO/IEC 5212 helpful in providing additional guidance during the decision-making process for the use, sharing and exchange of data
ISO/IEC 5212:2024 Data usage — Guidance for data usage (in Figure 4)	Published in April 2024	This document provides guidance on the decision-making processes for data usage, being the use, sharing and exchange of data. This document is intended to provide high-level guidance to data users, organizations, and individuals to assist in realising the benefits from data usage while managing risks
ISO/IEC 19763-3:2020 Metamodel framework for interoperability (MFI) Part 3: Metamodel for ontology registration (in Figure 4)	Published in October 2020	<p>This document specifies the metamodel that provides a facility to register administrative and evolution information related to ontologies.</p> <p>The metamodel is intended to promote interoperability among application systems, by providing administrative and evolution information related to ontologies, accompanied with standardized ontology repositories that register ontologies themselves in specific languages.</p> <p>This document does not specify the metamodels of ontologies expressed in specific languages and the mappings among them.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Continuum from data to information, to knowledge, to wisdom (DIKW)
 - **Gap:** characteristics of trustworthiness are numerous, from very technical characteristic (e.g. security) to very societal characteristic (e.g. ethics)
 - **Roadmap:** applying trustworthiness-by-design to ecosystems involving multiple organisations.
- Trustworthiness
 - **Gap:** ensuring a trustworthy collection, creation and usage of data
 - **Roadmap:** define methods for trustworthiness characterization and governance of data lifecycle.

3.2.8 Artificial Intelligence

Table 8 provides a selected lists of standards from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, SC42, and CEN-CENELEC JTC21.

Table 9. AI standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 42117-1 PWI AI — Trustworthiness Fact Labels (in Figure 4)	Under discussion	<p>Currently proposing two parts:</p> <p>Part 1: Principles and general requirements on trustworthiness fact statements and programmes for AI system and model</p> <p>This document establishes principles and specifies general requirements that are applicable to all types of AI system- and model-related trustworthiness fact statements and AI trustworthiness fact statement programmes. AI Trustworthiness fact statements result from AI trustworthiness fact statement programmes and include</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		<p>self-declared trustworthiness fact claims, AI trustworthiness fact labels (TFLs), AI quantitative facts declarations (QFDs), AI developer technical cards (DTCs) and footprint communications.</p> <p>This document is intended to be used in conjunction with other standards in the ISO/IEC 42117 family.</p> <p>Part2: Self-declared trustworthiness fact claims (Type II AI trust worthiness labelling)</p> <p>This document specifies requirements for self-declared trustworthiness fact claims, including statements, symbols and graphics, regarding products. It further describes selected terms commonly used in trustworthiness fact claims and gives qualifications for their use. This International Standard also describes a general evaluation and verification methodology for self-declared trustworthiness fact claims and specific evaluation and verification methods for the selected claims in this International Standard.</p> <p>This document does not preclude, override, or in any way change, legally required trustworthiness information, claims or labelling, or any other applicable legal requirements.</p>
ISO/IEC 27091 Artificial intelligence – Privacy protection (in Figure 4)	Final draft international standard	<p>This document provides guidance for organizations to address privacy risks in artificial intelligence (AI) systems, including machine learning (ML) models. This document helps organizations to identify privacy risks throughout the AI system lifecycle, and establishes mechanisms to evaluate the consequences and treatment of such risks.</p> <p>This document is applicable to all types and sizes of organizations that develop or use AI systems, including public and private companies, government entities, and not-for-profit organizations.</p>
ISO/IEC 8183 AI – Data life cycle framework (in Figure 4)	Published in July 2023	<p>This document defines the stages and identifies associated actions for data processing throughout the artificial intelligence (AI) system life cycle, including acquisition, creation, development, deployment, maintenance and decommissioning. This document does not define specific services, platforms or tools. This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size or nature, that use data in the development and use of AI systems.</p>
ISO/IEC 42103 AI – Overview of synthetic data in the context of AI systems (in Figure 4)	Under development	<p>This document provides an overview of synthetic data concepts, methods, uses and considerations in the context of AI systems. It describes uses of synthetic data and unique challenges presented by these uses. Its use within the data life cycle including risks associated with synthetic data and data quality characteristics. Use of synthetic data in different industries and sustainability issues that arise during synthetic data activities.</p>

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 27090 AI – Guidance for addressing security threats and compromises in artificial intelligence systems (in Figure 4)	Final draft international standard	<p>This document provides guidance for organizations to address security threats and failures specific to artificial intelligence (AI) systems. The guidance in this document aims to provide information to organizations to help them better understand the consequences of security threats specific to AI systems, throughout their life cycle, and descriptions of how to detect and mitigate such threats.</p> <p>This document is applicable to all types and sizes of organizations, including public and</p>
prEN 18229-1 AI trustworthiness framework - Part 1: Logging (in Figure 4)	Under approval	<p>This document provides terminology, concepts, requirements, and guidance for logging of AI systems. It is primarily intended for organizations placing on the market or putting into service AI systems and is not specific to any particular sector.</p>
prEN 18229-2 AI trustworthiness framework - Part 2: Accuracy and robustness (in Figure 4)	Under approval	<p>This document provides a framework for AI systems' trustworthiness which contains terminology, concepts, high-level horizontal requirements, guidance and a method to contextualize those to specific stakeholders, domains or applications. The high-level horizontal requirements address foundational aspects and characteristics of trustworthiness of AI systems. This document is primarily intended for organizations placing on the market or putting into service AI systems. Part 2 covers Accuracy and robustness.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Integration in architecture descriptions
 - **Gap:** lack of guidance in how to integrate AI, and lack of reference architecture focusing on AI
 - **Roadmap:** populating architecture standards with architecture patterns involving AI.
- Contextualisation of AI
 - **Gap:** guidance on how to support different contexts (specific application domains such as energy, health, manufacturing, specific technology contexts such as embedded systems, metaverse, digital systems)
 - **Roadmap:** define methods for contextualised requirements and assurance.

4. CEI asset-driven Standards

4.1 Guidelines

The myriads of standards makes it difficult for stakeholders is to identify standards and their dependencies. CEI-Sphere has proposed three types of standards of potential interest for CEI: architecture patterns, MIM profiles and information model profiles.

Architecture patterns

Research projects:

- Patterns are based on common foundations such as the [ISO/IEC 30141](https://www.iso.org/standard/72411.html) IoT reference architecture (published and freely available), or the [ISO/IEC 30188](https://www.iso.org/standard/72412.html) Digital twin reference architecture, and
- Architecture foundations can be contextualised through the addition of patterns which in turn provide capabilities.

Figure 5 illustrates a clear and hierarchical relationship between foundational standards, architecture patterns, and capabilities:

- A pattern can be a specialisation of a foundation. For example, a digital twin reference architecture can be considered a specialised pattern of a broader IoT reference architecture.
- A pattern can also be a specialisation of another pattern. For instance, a smart manufacturing digital twin pattern is a more specific version of the general digital twin pattern.
- A pattern provides a capability. For example, a data space connector pattern provides the specific technical capability of connecting to a data space

It is a fundamental conceptual model that will drive the publication of future architecture standards based on the smart standard initiative².

Figure 5 – Architecture pattern relationship with capabilities

² <https://www.iso.org/smart>

Architecture, MIMs and Information Models

Figure 6 presents an example of standards mapping and dependencies:

- Patterns A, B, C are architecture pattern standards, representing for instance CEI patterns,
 - Examples of patterns are client-server, publish subscribe, digital twin, federated learning.
- MIM profile 1, MIM profile 2, and MIM profile 3 are MIM profile standards,
- Information model profile X, Information model profile Y, Information model profile Z are information model profile standards.

In Figure 6, pattern A uses MIM profile 1 and 2, MIM profile 1 uses information model profiles X and Y, while MIM profile 3 uses information model Y.

Figure 6 – Example of standards dependencies

4.2 Supporting materials

4.2.1 Architecture patterns

Architecture patterns are used in system and software engineering to foster reusability of building blocks. They are the most important standardisation instrument to promote technology building blocks.

Several related definitions can be cited:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7 (software and system engineering) defines a [design pattern](#) as follows:
Description of the problem and the essence of its solution to enable the solution to be reused in different settings
- Wikipedia defines a [architecture pattern](#) as the capturing of architectural design ideas as archetypal and reusable descriptions.

Table 10 describes activities related to architecture patterns.

Table 10. Architecture patterns activities

Activity	Status	Description
Work carried out by the system and software engineering community.	Well established field	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> INCOSE, the international council on systems engineering, is the leading community with about 26000 members, is providing leading contributions on the topic, for instance within the MBSE (model-based system engineering) patterns working group. OMG, the object management group is a standard development organisation which contributes to the definition of key standards such as UML (Uniform Modelling Language). OMG is also managing DTC (Digital Twin Consortium). It includes the OMG's Systems Engineering Domain Special Interest Group (SE DSIG) which has formed the joint INCOSE/OMG MBSE Patterns Working Group.
Architecture patterns in standardisation.	Work started in November 2024 in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC41	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 (IoT and digital twins) is currently working on a roadmap towards the publication of patterns as standards in the advisory group AG 35 (pattern repository) co-chaired by Dave Board and Antonio Kung. A PWI (Preliminary Work Item) on architecture considerations for IoT, edge and cloud, edited by Antonio Kung and Lara Lopez on behalf of the OpenContinuum support action, and submitted through the AIOTI liaison with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41, is underway since June 2024.

Gaps and roadmaps

- Integration in architecture descriptions
 - **Gap:** lack of guidance in how to combine architecture patterns. The composition of pattern in standards has not yet been demonstrated. While it currently addressed in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41/WG 3 (IoT foundational standards), and support for implementation is not available yet.
 - **Roadmap:** approach for composition of patterns which would be based on [smart standards](#). Note that a clear roadmap has not been defined because of the investment needs. We foresee a need to work on standards on guidance for the creation of architecture standard patterns?
- Contextualisation
 - **Gap:** Contextualisation of foundational architecture standards (such as ISO/IEC 30141 or ISO/30188) by adding patterns in application domains will require coordination and governance during standardisation activities.
 - **Roadmap:** provides guidance on how to create architecture profiles integrating contextualisation needs.

4.2.2 Minimum interoperability mechanisms

Activities

MIM (Minimum Interoperability Mechanism) profiles are the defining feature of the narrow layer in the CEI hourglass model, as detailed in the text box on the topic. Originally developed to solve interoperability challenges in smart cities, these profiles provide a standardised way to access underlying capabilities.

Table 11 describes activities related to minimum interoperability mechanisms.

Table 11. MIM activities

Standards and activities	Status	Description
ITU-T Y.4505 (08/2024) Minimal interoperability mechanisms for smart and sustainable cities and communities.	Published in August 2024	<p>This Recommendation defines minimal interoperability mechanisms (MIMs) as a method of specifying sets of requirements that will enable minimal but sufficient interoperability for smart and sustainable cities and communities, along with describing one or more mechanisms that address those requirements, and providing guidance on achieving relevant interoperability between those mechanisms and on conformance and compliance testing. The scope of this Recommendation includes the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concept of MIMs; • Required characteristics of a MIM; • The structure of MIM.
OASC MIMs specification v8	2025	<p>The minimal interoperability mechanisms (MIMs) enable a minimal but sufficient level of interoperability for data, systems, and services specifically in the context of smart city solutions.</p> <p>The intended audience for this document are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution providers that wish to make sure their solutions are interoperable with other and allow fluid exchange of data within a Smart Cities and Communities context. • Procurers that wish to procure solutions that are future-proof and allow cost-effective integration within an existing Smart Cities and Communities Information and Communication Technology (ICT) architecture.
MIM0 Accessing data	Component of OASC MIMs specification v8	<p>This MIM helps cities and communities to overcome the challenges of accessing data that currently reside in silos and are often fragmented across different systems and locked away by making recommendations of how data should be made accessible so it can be easier accessed and reused in an interoperable way.</p>
MIM1: Interlinking Data	Component of OASC MIMs specification v8	<p>This MIM helps cities and communities address the challenges of disconnected data sources spread across diverse systems and contexts.</p>

Standards and activities	Status	Description
MIM2: Representing Data	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	<p>This MIMs allows cities and communities to overcome the challenges of working with data that are represented in different ways by providing recommendations for the use of consistent and machine-readable representations of data so that data from various sources can be efficiently used with confidence across the organisation and shared with collaborators as part of a local data ecosystem.</p>
MIM3: Exchanging Data	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	<p>Data is the lifeblood of urban innovation. Many cities and communities are now leveraging data to make better decisions about prioritising scarce public funding, improving service delivery to their citizens, and improving the overall quality of life in the city. Increasingly relevant data is not only sourced and shared across different city departments but also exchanged with external organisations to improve local innovation capacity and to access critical information not available in-house.</p> <p>Over the past decade or more, many cities and communities used open data initiatives or ad-hoc data sharing agreements to advance data use and sharing across their organisation and with relevant stakeholders. However, they find these approaches are no longer sufficient. Publishing data openly on a public data portal does not suit the many types of sensitive data (e.g., commercial or personal data) cities and communities are now working with. Bespoke bilateral data sharing agreements are cumbersome to agree, set up and maintain, and do not scale well. As the diversity and complexity of data collaborations grow, cities and communities need to find more differentiated ways of data sharing.</p> <p>Cities and communities are now exploring new ways of managing their local data ecosystem. This includes ensuring that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data is discoverable in a local data ecosystem, no matter what parties the data comes from or what systems it resides on • data is accessible in a local data ecosystem to all parties who are entitled to access the data. • data is adequately permissioned in a local data ecosystem, so that parties using the data are fully aware of what they can or cannot do with it. • data and its exchange can be trusted in a local data ecosystem. This includes both trust in the data provided as part of a data exchange and trust in the parties participating in the exchange. <p>The MIM3 working group aims to help cities and communities create common guidelines that make data sharing and collaboration more effective in a local data ecosystem.</p>

Standards and activities	Status	Description
		<p>It tackles the challenges of how data can be stewarded and used across diverse systems of different organisations into a common data ecosystem that enables data providers and users to exchange data in a trusted way with confidence and derive value from it. It also aims to ensure that interactions related to data exchange in different local data ecosystems of other cities and communities are interoperable.</p>
MIM4: Personal Data	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	<p>MIM4 focuses on Personal Data Management in other words how to provide easy to use methods for individuals to control which data sets/attributes they want to share with solution, application, or service providers under transparent circumstances, enabling trust between the different parties.</p> <p>There are many initiatives seeking to provide personal data management solutions, but these are primarily in the pilot or development phase, and this has led to a fragmented marketplace.</p> <p>The aims of the different initiatives overlap but are not necessarily identical. Some projects focus just on personal data management, others, such as RUDI, aim to support wider data sharing ecosystems, but with personal data management being a key feature.</p> <p>There are two networks of providers – MyData and Solid, which each follow different high-level methodologies. Even within each of these two networks, there are significant differences in the technical and processes used by different projects and so individual implementations are not necessarily interoperable.</p> <p>There are a number of initiatives outside of these networks developing their own technical solutions.</p> <p>The role of MIM4 is to identify the key capabilities required and identify pivotal points of interoperability between the different solutions to help build confidence and support implementation.</p>
MIM6: Securing Data	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	<p>As cities become smarter and more technology-driven, they become a target for cyber-attacks with significant consequences in terms of costs and loss of services. In order to deliver reliable digital services for citizens, cities have to continuously evaluate the cyber risks and to put in place security measures to prepare for cyber-attacks.</p> <p>The first version of MIM 6 focuses on addressing interoperability for secure data transfer. The limited scope is to get progress, and later iterations can and probably will expand the scope.</p>
MIM7: Geospatial Data	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	<p>MIM7 aims to provide Minimal Interoperability Mechanisms related to geospatial data, to tackle the challenge faced by cities and communities of being able to</p>

Standards and activities	Status	Description																									
		integrate and transfer data between internal and external IT systems. It also takes into account the fact that spatial assets need to be accessed as linked data by many IT- and IoT-systems, and over a long period of time, and thus the vital role of the use of persistent identifiers.																									
MIM8: Local Digital Twins	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	<p>This MIM describes interoperability in terms of the application domain of Local Digital Twins. In support of describing minimal interoperability mechanisms in this domain the MIM8 working group put forward a minimal definition of Local (or Urban) Digital Twins. This does not preclude any other definitions to be valid, and we recognise that depending on applications features may vary.</p> <p>A Local (or Urban) Digital Twin is a digital representation of physical assets, systems, or processes in a defined local context (e.g., city, district, building, industry, port, airport). It leverages either on historical data, near real-time data, or real-time data enables visualization, analysis, simulation and reasoning for supporting decision-making.</p> <p>The working group understands the diversity of local digital twins depending on their functionalities. Below is a table of different functionalities of a Local (or Urban) Digital Twin can have and as such are commonly categorised as: Awareness LDT, Experimental LDT, Predictive LDT, and Intelligent LDT.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="791 1182 1426 1581"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="791 1182 1098 1379">Category of LDC</th> <th data-bbox="1098 1182 1187 1379">Visualisation</th> <th data-bbox="1187 1182 1267 1379">Simulation</th> <th data-bbox="1267 1182 1347 1379">Analytics*</th> <th data-bbox="1347 1182 1426 1379">Autonomous</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="791 1379 1098 1429">Awareness</td> <td data-bbox="1098 1379 1187 1429">x</td> <td data-bbox="1187 1379 1267 1429"></td> <td data-bbox="1267 1379 1347 1429"></td> <td data-bbox="1347 1379 1426 1429"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="791 1429 1098 1478">Experimental</td> <td data-bbox="1098 1429 1187 1478">x</td> <td data-bbox="1187 1429 1267 1478">x</td> <td data-bbox="1267 1429 1347 1478"></td> <td data-bbox="1347 1429 1426 1478"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="791 1478 1098 1527">Predictive</td> <td data-bbox="1098 1478 1187 1527">x</td> <td data-bbox="1187 1478 1267 1527">x</td> <td data-bbox="1267 1478 1347 1527">x</td> <td data-bbox="1347 1478 1426 1527"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="791 1527 1098 1581">Intelligent</td> <td data-bbox="1098 1527 1187 1581">x</td> <td data-bbox="1187 1527 1267 1581">x</td> <td data-bbox="1267 1527 1347 1581">x</td> <td data-bbox="1347 1527 1426 1581">x</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>While we align with commonly agreed definitions (such as the one above), communities have expressed that simulations require more complex work process than analytics, and hence, experimental digital twins are viewed more complex as predictive LDTs.</p> <p>We discern the following additional functionalities across the following layers:</p> <p>Layer 1: Data acquisition (historic/near real-time/real-time data)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> sensing 	Category of LDC	Visualisation	Simulation	Analytics*	Autonomous	Awareness	x				Experimental	x	x			Predictive	x	x	x		Intelligent	x	x	x	x
Category of LDC	Visualisation	Simulation	Analytics*	Autonomous																							
Awareness	x																										
Experimental	x	x																									
Predictive	x	x	x																								
Intelligent	x	x	x	x																							

Standards and activities	Status	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • extraction • synthetic data generation <p>Layer 2: Connectivity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APIs • protocols • file sharing <p>Layer 3: Data pre-processing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • semantics • interoperability • aggregation <p>Layer 4: Analysis & simulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Models • Physics-based simulations <p>Layer 5: Communication of results (visualisation)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dashboard • Multi-dimensional visualisation • natural language interface (like chatbot) • VR <p>Layer 6: Decision-making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prescription • support • automation
OASC interoperability	Component of OASC MIMs specification V8	Provides information on interoperability and governance

Gaps and roadmaps

- Integration in architecture descriptions
 - **Gap:** While OASC provide significant insight on MIM mechanisms, the process of define associated profiles is not yet widely adopted. We foresee the need to work on standards on guidance for the creation of MIM profiles
 - **Roadmap:** Use the hourglass model to justify and describe interoperability profiles.
- Contextualisation
 - **Gap:** The creation of profiles requires coordination and governance during standardisation activities.
 - **Roadmap:** Agree and maintain (improve) the governance process

4.2.3 Information model profiles

Activities

Information models are graphical and textual representation of entities and the relationships between them. Information models are a key instrument for interoperability. Information model profiles are critical to provide a single source of truth basis based on semantic interoperability based on ontologies.

Table 12 describes activities related to information models.

Table 12. Information model activities

Standards and activities	Status	Description
JRC code of conduct on energy smart appliances	Started in 2022. Is currently working on phase 2.	<p>Policy support for a wide-scale deployment of Energy Smart Appliances is a complex matter, crossing the fields of product and digital-related policy instruments. Any potential measure would not directly address energy efficiency but instead will essentially seek to certify a specific 'energy-smart' behaviour of products.</p> <p>This initiative, led by DG ENER and the Joint Research Centre, aims to propose a Code of Conduct (CoC) to the Energy Smart Appliances (ESA) manufacturers for adherence. The version 1.0 of the CoC for ESA is final, please, click here to download.</p> <p>The design of the CoC addresses two main challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The definition of the principles for data sharing among appliances, Energy Management Systems, EV chargers, aggregators, DSOs • The development of Interoperability requirements for ESA <p>Stakeholders (industry, NGOs, academia) and Member States authorities will be involved in this process. Involvement and communication with stakeholders will be undertaken in a combination of questionnaires, webinars and physical meetings. The coordination of stakeholders will be carried out jointly by DG ENER and the JRC.</p>
A joint AIOTI/StandICT/Intnet report: Evolution of interoperability standards	Published in November 2024	<p>This report provides first a landscape on interoperability standards, focusing on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT standards, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ distributed systems, ○ cloud computing, and • internet of things and digital twin, and • application domain standards, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ health, ○ energy. <p>It then elaborates on the changing context concerning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the complexity of ecosystems or socio-technical systems, • the increasing number of policies and regulations, and • the evolution of interoperability frameworks. <p>It then describes the expected evolution of standardisation practice for interoperability, consisting of moves towards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the interoperability of standards,

Standards and activities	Status	Description														
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the interoperability of concepts and architectures across multiple standardisation instances, and the interoperability of systems in complex ecosystems. <p>The report concludes with a call to anticipate a new ecosystem of standardisation practices.</p>														
A joint AIOTI/Intnet report: Information Models Coordination and Governance Standardisation Recommendations	Published in November 2024	<p>This document explains and highlights the need for coordination on information models promoted by IEC, ISO or ITU-T standardisation organizations.</p> <p>It first describes the main concepts and details the required coordination specifically for information models and then at the cross-domain level, which leads to 3 recommendations on interoperability:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="756 725 1394 1182"> <thead> <tr> <th>Concerns</th> <th>Recommendations</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Information models</td> <td>R: Standardisation committees should engage in coordination and governance activities on information models selected as relevant.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cross domain</td> <td>R: Standardisation committees should set up cross-domain coordination.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SDO</td> <td>R: SDOs should adapt their ecosystem to better handle standardised information models across their whole life cycle (from their creation, to their publication including their maintenance)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Then, it focuses on the specific case of SAREF and the required coordination, in particular around energy and smart grid, which leads to 2 additional recommendations for coordination:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="756 1332 1394 1572"> <thead> <tr> <th>Concerns</th> <th>Recommendations</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>SAREF</td> <td>R: Create a SAREF information model coordination and governance.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SAREF</td> <td>R: Host the SAREF information model coordination by an existing structure, e.g. AIOTI</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Concerns	Recommendations	Information models	R: Standardisation committees should engage in coordination and governance activities on information models selected as relevant.	Cross domain	R: Standardisation committees should set up cross-domain coordination.	SDO	R: SDOs should adapt their ecosystem to better handle standardised information models across their whole life cycle (from their creation, to their publication including their maintenance)	Concerns	Recommendations	SAREF	R: Create a SAREF information model coordination and governance.	SAREF	R: Host the SAREF information model coordination by an existing structure, e.g. AIOTI
Concerns	Recommendations															
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SAREF	R: Create a SAREF information model coordination and governance.															
SAREF	R: Host the SAREF information model coordination by an existing structure, e.g. AIOTI															

Gaps and roadmaps

- Siloed practice
 - **Gap:** the standardisation ecosystem practice on information models is siloed. It does not support well the development of cross-domain standards. It does not support transversal work on concept and architecture standards that would ensure interoperability of concepts and of architectures across domain. It does not support assurance and conformity assessment standardisation involving items defined by multiple standardisation instances.
 - **Roadmap:** Set a cross-domain practice.
- Coordination and governance activities on information models standards
 - **Gap:** They are often neglected in particular when multiple standardisation instances are involved (for instance the [JRC code of conduct on energy smart appliances](#) involves ETSI work on [SAREF](#) and IEC work on [IEC 61850](#))
 - **Roadmap:** Agree, define, invest and maintain (improve) on a governance process

4.2.4 Managing CEI Assets

Activities

Table 13 provides a selected lists of standards and CEI assets from ISO/IEC TC251, JTC 1/SC 7, SC41.

Table 13. Asset standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 19770-1:2017 IT asset management — Part 1: IT asset management systems — Requirements	Published in December 2017	<p>ISO/IEC 19770-1:2017 specifies requirements for an IT asset management system within the context of the organization.</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-1:2017 can be applied to all types of IT assets and by all types and sizes of organizations.</p> <p>NOTE 1 This document is intended to be used for managing IT assets in particular, but it can also be applied to other asset types. It can be suitable, in whole or in part, for managing embedded software and firmware, however its use for these purposes has not been determined. It is not intended for managing information assets per se, i.e. it is not intended for managing information as an asset independent of hardware and software assets. Certain types of data and information are covered, such as data and information about IT assets in scope, and depending on how the scope is defined, it can cover digital information content assets. See the Introduction for an explanation about IT assets.</p> <p>NOTE 2 This document does not specify financial, accounting, or technical requirements for managing specific IT asset types.</p> <p>NOTE 3 For the purposes of this document, the term "IT asset management system" is used to refer to a management system for IT asset management.</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-1:2017 is a discipline-specific extension of ISO 55001:2014, with changes, and is not a sector-specific</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		application of that International Standard. ISO 55001:2014 is intended to be used for managing physical assets in particular, but it can also be applied to other asset types. This document specifies requirements for the management of IT assets which are additional to those specified in ISO 55001:2014. Conformance to this document does not imply conformance to ISO 55001:2014. ISO/IEC 19770-1:2017 can be used by internal and external parties to assess the organization's ability to meet the organization's own IT asset management requirements.
ISO/IEC 19770-2:2015 Software asset management — Part 2: Software identification tag	Published in October 2015	ISO/IEC 19770-2:2015 establishes specifications for tagging software to optimize its identification and management. This part of ISO/IEC 19770 applies to the following. <p>a) Tag producers: these organizations and/or tools create software identification (SWID) tags for use by others in the market. A tag producer may be part of the software creator organization, the software licensor organization, or be a third-party organization. These organizations and/or tools can broadly be broken down into the following categories.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platform providers: entities responsible for the computer or hardware device and/or associated operating system, virtual environment, or application platform, on which software may be installed or run. Platform providers which support this part of ISO/IEC 19770 may additionally provide tag management capabilities at the level of the platform or operating system. Software providers: entities that create, license, or distribute software. For example, software creators, independent software developers, consultants, and repackagers of previously manufactured software. Software creators may also be in-house software developers. Tag tool providers: entities that provide tools to create software identification tags. For example, tools within development environments that generate software identification tags, or installation tools that may create tags on behalf of the installation process, and/or desktop management tools that may create tags for installed software that did not originally have a software identification tag. <p>b) Tag consumers: these tools and/or organizations utilize information from SWID tags and are typically broken down into the following two major categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> software consumers: entities that purchase, install, and/or otherwise consume software; IT discovery and processing tool providers: entities that provide tools to collect, store, and process software identification tags. These tools may be targeted at a variety of different market segments, including software security, compliance, and logistics.

Standard	Status	Description
		<p>ISO/IEC 19770-2:2015 does not prescribe Information Technology Asset Management (ITAM) or other IT-related processes required for reconciliation of software entitlements with software identification tags or other IT requirements.</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-2:2015 is not intended to conflict either with any organization's policies, procedures or standards or with any national or international laws and regulations.</p>
<p>ISO/IEC 19770-3:2016 IT asset management — Part 3: Entitlement schema</p>	<p>Published in April 2016</p>	<p>ISO/IEC 19770-3:2016 establishes a set of terms and definitions which may be used when discussing software entitlements (an important part of software licenses). It also provides specifications for a transport format which enables the digital encapsulation of software entitlements, including associated metrics and their management.</p> <p>This common set of terms and associated transport format is intended to facilitate the management of software entitlements. The intended benefits of the better management of entitlements include easier demonstration of proof of ownership, cost optimization of the use of entitlements and easier license compliance management.</p> <p>Furthermore, one of the benefits of having a standard for entitlement structure is that it may encourage the normalization by industry of names for and the details of, different types of entitlements. A common lexicon is critical to standardization and shared understanding. The terms in this part of ISO/IEC 19770 should form a part of that lexicon over time.</p> <p>It should be noted that within this text, attributes of an XML entity will be denoted with angle brackets, <attribute>. XML elements are noted with quotes, "Element".</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-3:2016 deals only with software entitlements, which are defined as the subset of software licenses that are concerned with usage rights. It is expected that the original documentation of licensing terms and conditions will be definitive for legal purposes, and will always take precedence over the Ent encapsulation.</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-3:2016 does not detail ITAM processes required for discovery and management of software (which is provided for in ISO/IEC 19770-1) or software identification tags (as defined by ISO/IEC 19770-2).</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-3:2016 does not consider identifying mechanisms for product activation.</p> <p>ISO/IEC 19770-3:2016 is not intended to conflict with any organization's policies, procedures and standards, or with any national laws and regulations. Any such conflict should be resolved before using this part of ISO/IEC 19770. In case</p>

Standard	Status	Description
		the conflict cannot be resolved, the specification shall not be implemented.
ISO/IEC 19770-4:2017 IT asset management — Part 4: Resource utilization measurement	Published in September 2017	<p>ISO/IEC 19770-4:2017 establishes specifications for an information structure to contain Resource Utilization Measurement information to facilitate IT asset management (ITAM).</p> <p>This document is applicable to all types of organization (for example, commercial enterprises, government agencies, and non-profit organizations).</p>
ISO/IEC TS 19770-10:2025 IT asset management — Part 10: Guidance for implementing ITAM	Published in June 2025	<p>This document covers the following information technology asset management (ITAM) system processes:</p> <p>a) management system processes for the overall system of IT asset management (not described in ISO/IEC 19770-1 in detail), which are specified in this document for comprehensive coverage and consistency of explanations; these include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understanding the external context and shareholder needs (7.1, 7.2 and 10.2); • leadership, policy and organization (10.3); • establishing and maintaining the management system (10.4); • planning and risk management (10.5); • support (including resources, competence, awareness, and communication – 10.6); • executing functional and life cycle processes (10.7); • performance evaluation and improvement (10.8); <p>b) functional management processes for IT assets (not described in ISO/IEC 19770-1 in detail), which are cross-cutting processes that integrate with life-cycle processes for IT assets and which are shared with most IT management system standards, though sometimes slightly differently grouped; these include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • change management (11.2; also required by ISO/IEC 19770-1); • data management; • license management; • security management; • relationship and contract management; • financial management; • service level management; • other risk management; <p>c) life cycle management processes for IT assets as specified in ISO/IEC 19770-1, which are grouped and named slightly differently by different methodologies; these include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • specification; • development; • acquisition; • release; • deployment;

Standard	Status	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> operation; retirement. <p>This document is applicable to all ITAM implementations. This document can be applied to all types of IT assets and by all types and sizes of organizations.</p>
ISO/IEC DIS 19770-5 IT asset management — Part 5: Overview and vocabulary	Draft international standard	<p>ISO/IEC 19770-5:2015 provides</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> an overview of the ISO/IEC 19770 family of standards, an introduction to IT asset management (ITAM) and software asset management (SAM), a brief description of the foundation principles and approaches on which SAM is based, and consistent terms and definitions for use throughout the ISO/IEC 19770 family of standards. <p>ISO/IEC 19770-5:2015 is applicable to all types of organization (e.g. commercial enterprises, government agencies, and non-profit organizations).</p>
ISO/IEC 19770-4:2017 IT asset management — Part 4: Resource utilization measurement	Published in septembre 2017	<p>ISO/IEC 19770-4:2017 establishes specifications for an information structure to contain Resource Utilization Measurement information to facilitate IT asset management (ITAM).</p> <p>This document is applicable to all types of organization (for example, commercial enterprises, government agencies, and non-profit organizations).</p>
PWI TR JTC1-SC41-36 Considerations for the life cycle of IoT assets	Underway	<p>This document provides guidance on the considerations for the life cycle of IoT assets by analysing IoT assets.</p>

Table 14 provides a selected lists of standards on assurance from ISO/IEC TC251, JTC 1/SC 7, SC41.

Table 14. Asset assurance standards

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC 19770-11:2021 IT asset management — Part 11: Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of IT asset management systems	Published in June 2021	<p>This document specifies requirements and provides guidance for certification bodies providing audit and certification of an ITAMS in accordance with ISO/IEC 19770-1. It does not change the requirements specified in ISO/IEC 19770-1.</p> <p>This document can also be used by accreditation bodies for the accreditation of certification bodies. However, this document does not specify requirements or provides guidance for accreditation bodies to audit certification bodies.</p> <p>A certification body providing ITAMS certification is expected to be able to demonstrate fulfilment of the requirements specified in this document, in addition to the requirements in ISO/IEC 17021-1.</p>

Standard	Status	Description
ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-1:2025 Vocabulary and concepts	Published in December 2025	<p>This document defines assurance-related terms and establishes an organized set of concepts to form a basis for shared understanding in the field of assurance. It benefits users of ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-2, ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-3 and ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-4.</p> <p>Vocabulary and concepts for assurance of a service being operated and managed on an ongoing basis is not covered in this document.</p> <p>While essential to assurance practice, details regarding exactly how to measure, demonstrate or analyse particular properties are not covered.</p>
ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-2:2022 Assurance case	Published in November 2022	<p>This document specifies requirements for structure terminology of assurance cases.</p> <p>This document is applicable for developing and maintaining assurance cases.</p>
ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-4:2021 Assurance in the life cycle	Published in May 2021	<p>This document provides guidance and recommendations for assurance of a selected claim about the system-of-interest by achieving the claim and showing the achievement. The guidance and recommendations are given in a system assurance process view on top of ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 and a software assurance process view on top of ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207.</p>
ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-4:2021 Assurance in the life cycle	Published in May 2021	<p>This document provides guidance and recommendations for assurance of a selected claim about the system-of-interest by achieving the claim and showing the achievement. The guidance and recommendations are given in a system assurance process view on top of ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 and a software assurance process view on top of ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207.</p>

Gaps and roadmaps

- Governance, assurance
 - **Gap:** IT assets include multiple stakeholders and it is important to set up a governance and assurance on a CEI asset. This also depends on the context when building a trusted CEI asset.
 - **Roadmap:** define a CEI asset management framework including governance and assurance capability and standardise it.
- Business management
 - **Gap:** Best business practice for CEI assets including several stakeholders.
 - **Roadmap:** define a CEI asset management framework including business management and standardise it.

5. Conclusions and next steps

5.1 Next Stage: CEI sphere-driven Standards

The need for contextualisation shows that domain driven standards are important. To this end CEI-Sphere came up with three community drive groups (or three spheres):

- Energy and infrastructure resilience
- Mobility, logistics and software defined vehicle
- Industrial optimization and productivity

It is planned in a later version of this document to provide a landscape document that is drive by the spheres.

5.2 Using the CEI-Sphere backbone toolkit

In order get an understanding on CEI-Sphere-driven standards, CEI-Sphere will use the CEI-Sphere backbone toolkit (defined in CEI-Sphere Deliverable [D4.1 \(CEI tech backbone toolkit for an open edge ecosystem. Checks & balances through a holistic assurance framework\)](#)). The toolkit (TK) consists of the following elements

- TK1: Ecosystems identification process,
- TK2: Ecosystem high-level description process,
- TK3: CEI ecosystem analysis process,
- TK4: CEI ecosystem trust label analysis process.

Figure 7 – Toolkit elements

When TK3 is reached, an update will be made to that TK4 can identify what it takes to create an impact through a trust labelling approach. Table 15 lists projects that can apply the toolkit.

Table 15. Projects involved in using the toolkit

Project	Description	Support
O-CEI	Through the spread of digitalisation, the Internet of things (IoT) has become increasingly crucial to the everyday functioning of logistics chains, infrastructure, business and more, driving novel solutions and innovations that benefit a wide range of services and sectors. In this context, the EU-funded O-CEI project aims to enhance Europe’s competitiveness and strategic autonomy in this sector, recognising the global significance of open cloud-edge IoT. It plans to achieve this by supporting eight pilots in key sectors through the introduction of novel technologies, frameworks and improved data sharing, leveraging shared developments to strengthen each pilot and maximise its potential.	By CEI-Sphere
COP-PILOT	The integration of edge computing, advanced 5G, and decentralised processing enables private edge ecosystems with transformative potential across industries.	By CEI-Sphere

Project	Description	Support
	<p>However, fully harnessing the benefits of edge-level intelligent management requires specialised platform development and cross-sector collaboration. The EU-funded COP-PILOT project aims to address this by developing a Collaborative Open Platform framework to orchestrate end-to-end services across multiple industries. This flexible platform will support secure, automated, and intelligent management of diverse sectors. By integrating technologies such as IoT platforms and core infrastructure, the framework will foster collaboration across the computing continuum. Additionally, it will facilitate advanced cross-sector applications through innovative network services that enhance security and resource efficiency.</p>	
Twin-EU	<p>Europe faces the imperative to transition to renewable energy sources and enhance the resilience and cost-effectiveness of its infrastructure. Digital twins (DT) emerge as tools for system operators and market participants to coordinate their operations. The development of a federated ecosystem of DT solutions on a European scale has become crucial, allowing each operator to make independent implementation decisions while ensuring interoperability. The EU-funded TwinEU project aims to develop new technologies and establish the necessary conditions for interoperability. It aims to create a European data exchange core supported by interfaces to the energy data space currently in development. Leveraging advanced modelling and AI tools, the project seeks to deliver a digital replica of the energy infrastructure that can be tested and activated.</p>	By Trialog as member of the advisory board of Twin-EU
Hedge-IoT	<p>As our world increasingly relies on renewable energy sources, energy systems face unprecedented challenges, and there's a need for new approaches and thorough transformation in common practices. The EU-funded HEDGE-IoT project aims to revolutionise the digitalisation of European energy systems by exploiting the advantages of IoT technologies, deployed at different levels of the power systems, through an interoperable and standardised digital framework. Bridging the edge-cloud continuum through computational orchestration and federated learning traits, the development of semantic enablers and AI/ML systems lies at the centre of the project's activities. The HEDGE-IoT ecosystem will pave the way towards increased grid flexibility, enhanced hosting capacity of renewable energy sources, and a more robust and resilient power system operation. Additional objectives are to expand market opportunities and promote advancements in IoT standardisation.</p>	By Trialog as partner of both CEI-Sphere and Hedge-IoT
LICORICE	<p>The global digital transformation driven by AI, Big Data, Metaverses, and Web3 presents both opportunities and challenges for EU citizens and businesses, including a surge in cyber-attacks and data abuse. Maintaining trust through robust data protection is crucial for securing digital services and developing EU data spaces. The EU-funded LICORICE project aims to provide highly advanced and reliable self-sovereign identity and privacy-preserving toolsets, offering tools for secure identity management and data sharing. The project will validate its results through two piloting iterations in Cyber Threat Intelligence and eHealth services, contributing to the EU's digital sovereignty.</p>	By Trialog as partner of both CEI-Sphere and Hedge-IoT

5.3 Next steps and foreseen future impact

The application of the backbone toolkit will allow for the provision of a standard landscape that is more domain oriented, i.e. reflecting the CEI-Spheres outcomes.